

Determinant of Family Background Variable on Career Choice of Secondary School Students in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract: *The study investigated determinants of family background variables on the career choice of secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study is to determine which of the family background variable that influences the career choice of secondary school in Ekiti State. To also find out the degree at which each of the variables influences the career choice of these students. Two questions were raised to guide the study with one null hypothesis. Descriptive of survey design was employed in the study. The population was all senior secondary school students where 500 students were sampled through stratified and Simple Random Sampling Methods. A self-designed instrument named family background variables and career choice questionnaires (FBVCCQ) was used to collect relevant information. The instrument was validated through test-retest with the reliability coefficient of 0.78. The instrument was administered and collected immediately. The collected data were analysed using frequency counts and percentage, ANOVA was used to test the only one hypothesis formulated. The results revealed that family background variables generally have an influence on the choice of career among the secondary school students in Ekiti State. The study suggested that career program should be put in place by the counselling unit in the school to help these students in preparing for their future.*

Keywords: *Family background variables, career choice, parents' decision, parents' occupation, parents' income, siblings influence, home types, family occupation.*

1. Introduction

In the early sixties and especially upon attaining independence in 1960, what seemed to be a primary concern of most Nigeria leaders then was how education would be accessible to all citizens of the newly independent nation. Education was seen as the necessary instrument essentially put in place to consolidate independence for securing the new nation against neo-colonialism and for making workable the newly established self-government in a multi-ethnic society. Mass education, at least to the level of literacy, was also seen by Nigeria leaders to be necessary to create a proper foundation for the smooth take of democratic government in Nigeria (Ige, 2015).

The desire to use education for nation building was and still very compelling. So predominant was the faith that the schools of Nigeria were not only meant for political socialization but also for other social functions and majorly for the nation economic growth. This is especially informed by the rapid change of the predominant traditional agricultural practice of the past to an industrial one today. Furthermore, the drift of people from rural areas to urban centres seems to have affected the family occupation of the present day career choice of Nigerian adolescents (Osakinle & Adegoroye, 2018). The problem of career choice seems to have implications for national development. In every society, the quality of workers, as well as their degree of job satisfaction, contributes directly or indirectly to economic stability and smooth running of the affairs of such a nation. In a situation where workers are unable to derive satisfaction from their job, frustration set in which accompanying decline in the productivity and civil unrest of workers in such a nation (Sorthout, Ten and Van, 2004).

Generally, it is believed that the primary motive behind the pursuit of various careers is the fundamental human need to make end meet and contribute to the nation economic growth. A number of variables seem to impact more strongly than others. What makes significantly influence the career preference of one person different from others (Sukoviatt, 1989). However, while it is difficult to determine the relative potency of those variables, it is true that there are some forms of interactions among them

where one modifies the other. While some of these variables are psychologically and biologically rooted, others have socio-economic undertones. Still, it is not uncommon for individuals to get into a career by accident or chance (Udoh and Sanni, 2012).

The family, irrespective of its type, monogamous (nuclear), polygamous or extended, constitute the primary social environment where the child first interacts to function. Omotere (2011) defined the family as a group of persons united by the ties of marriage, blood adoption, constituting a single household interacting and inter-communicating with each other on their respective roles of mother, father, husband, wife, brother, sister creating a common culture. Parental dynamic and interaction have been long assumed to play a significant role in their children's career development (Doublebell & Strewing, 2013). Parental involvement in the career choice of children begins early when they (parents) notice the abilities and interest of their children. Asamo (2014) have noticed that many parents are in the habits of determining virtually all-academic decision for their children. Some choose the school to attend, the books to read and even the subject to study in school. Oladele (2004) posited that parental education and socio-economic status seem to have an impact on student's career information provided by the parent's to children influence them in the choice based on the exposure of these parents.

Asamo (2014) in his contribution said parents who are well educated and professional in the different field could be better equipped to help their children with the understanding of the idea of where the course or discipline a child is interested could lead them for better career choice. This Asamo contribution was criticized that some children born and brought up in the home of illiterates and some semi educated are taking to a better career that suits their interest which contributes to their life. Eremie (2014). Also stress the contribution made by the family members of school adolescents, whereby, some student will directly or indirectly listen and see reasons to follow the family members' suggestions as regard to career choice. Some based their argument on the family career that they don't want to go to an extension, while some argued on inheritance, that is, to have

inherited the trait of the work or career from their parents. For example a business owner, or company owner who want their children or one of their child to take up the business or the company when their (parents) are old or after their death. Moratori and Smith (2015) in one of their study also support the view that a child that learns the occupation or career of their parents by following them to work may at later years take up the occupation as an inheritance to become a his\her career. This was what (Wang and Huguley, 2012) their studies found that career choices are inherited directly from parents.

Ezeani (2013) stated that through family influence everyone is exposed to value, attitudes, feelings and a climate for learning. This underscores why the family has a profound influence on the evaluative aspect of the child’s development including his judgment of which career to pursue. This support the view that a child raised in accordance with the values of the family and as the child grows he\she learns, internalizes and concretizes the behaviour patterns to which he\she is exposed. Madu (2011) postulated some relationship between children’s early rearing experiences and their occupational choice since children spend most of their years at home and naturally regard the family as their reference group with parents as significant figures. Purteil and Mchord (2013) classified parental work attitudes into four broad areas as follows, the silent attitude, the resentful altitude, the participating altitude and the candid altitude, children from these categories of the home will have a different attitude toward work assuming that other influential variables are kept constant. This suggests that the attitude towards work, parental occupation and educational also impact strongly on the occupational choice of children (Ogunlade & Akeredolu, 2012). Children raised in a home dominated by a certain occupation may be likely to be influenced by such an occupation. The high rate of competition for prestigious and lucrative occupations between the rich and poor families has seen rich parents compelling their children to train for the prestigious and lucrative position in order to maintain the status and for the poor families for liberation from their poor situation (Ezeani, 2013). The purpose of this study is set to determined the family background variables (i.e., parents influence, family occupation, parent income, stumbling motives, parent uncared attitude, intact home influence) on career choice of secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The significant of the study is for the guidance practitioners in Nigerian secondary school provide career guidance and counselling programmed that will help the students out of parent or family confusion as regard career choice and development. To also determine which of the family background variables that influences the career choice of the secondary students in Nigeria. Two questions were raised to guide the study.

- (1) What are the family background variables that are influencing the choice of career of secondary school students in Ekiti, state, Nigeria?
- (2) Would there be any significant difference in the family background variables and students choice of career?

Based on the research questions raised, one null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There will be no significant different in the family background variable and career choice of secondary school students.

2. Methodology

The study employed the use of descriptive research of survey type. The population for the study was all the senior secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample for the study was 500 students; these samples were selected through stratified and single random sampling techniques.

3. Research instrument

The instrument for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire named “Family Background Variables and Career Choice Questionnaire (FBVCCQ).” The instrument is of two sections; section A sought information on students bio-data while section B help to elicit information on family background variables and its influence on students career choice.

4. Validation of the instrument

The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured, while the test-re-test method was used to ascertain for the consistency of the instrument. However, the reliability coefficient of 0.78 was got, and this was adjudged to be high enough to determine the reliability of the instrument.

5. Administration of Instrument and Data Analysis

The instruments were administered on the respondents by the researcher in all the questionnaires were collected back. Frequently counts, percentage and mean scores were used to answer the research question raised, while, analysis of variance was used to test the formulated hypothesis.

6. Results

To determine the influence of family background variables on the career choice of secondary school students in Ekiti State. The scores collected were analyzed and described using frequency table and relative percentage for each variable raise to guide the study.

Question 1: What are the family background variables that are influencing the choice of choice career of secondary school students?

Table 1: Frequency count, percentage and mean scores showing the influence of family background variables on the career choice of respondents.

6.1. Family Background Variable

S/N	Variables	Agree		Disagree		Mean	Rank
		F	%	F	%		
1.	Parent decision	304	0.8	196	39.2	1.61	1st
2.	Parents occupation	206	41.2	294	58.8	1.41	5th

3.	Parents income	296	59.2	204	40.8	1.59	2nd
4.	Siblings influence	227	45.4	273	54.6	1.45	4th
5.	Home type (broken or intact)	152	30.4	348	69.6	1.30	6th
6.	Family occupation	290	58.0	210	42.0	1.58	3rd

6.2. Choice

Variable	Mean	PD	PO	PI	SI	HT	FO
Parents decisions(PD)	1.61						
Parents occupation(PO)	1.41	*					
Parents income(PI)	1.59	*	*				
Siblings influence(SI)	1.45	*	*	*			
Home type (intact or broken) (HT)	1.30	*	*	*	*		
Family occupation(FO)	1.58	*	*	*	*	*	

The table revealed that 60.8% of the respondents confirmed that their parent's decision influence their choice of career while 39.2% decline from parents is deciding for their career choice. Parents deciding the career choice of their children ranked higher as determinants of a students career choice as compared with other variables. Parents' income in the work they do rank second with 59.2% of the respondents supports the idea of talking to their parents' career while 40.8% of them declined. The table also revealed that family occupation that was ranked 3rd was a very important determiner of career choice of the respondents, 58% of others support the influence of family occupations as their career choice, while 42% opposed to the idea. It was also on record that 45.4% as revealed on the table that sibling contributes to the choice of career of some students while 54.6% of them negate the idea of taking to siblings' occupation or advice. This variable was ranked the 4th position among the family background variables that contribute to students influence in career choice. The 5th ranked variable was parents' occupation where 41.25% agree to as determinant of their career choice while 58.8% refused to follow the parents' occupation. The home type was ranked as 6th position among the variables considered for students career choice 30.4% of the respondents agree with the view that type of home where they come from dictates their career choice while 69.6% declined from the idea.

Question 2: There will be no significant difference in the Family Background Variables and Career Choice of Secondary School Students.

Table 2: ANOVA showing the significant difference in the family background variable and career choice of students.

Variables	ss	df	Ms	f-cal	f-tab
Between groups	96054.119	5	19210.823		
Within groups	130933.25	265	499.088	38.9	2.65
Total	226987.45	270			

P<0.05 (significant)

The table revealed that f-calculated was 39.9 while its corresponding table value was 2.65 at 0.05 level of significance since the calculated value was higher than the table value; the null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This revealed that there are significant differences in the family background variables and career choice of secondary school students in the area of study.

To determine where the differences occurred a post hoc test of the one way ANOVA was carried out using turkey's multiple range tests.

Table 3: post-hoc test: turkey's multiple comparison tests on the family background and variable and career.

Table 3 showed that there is a significant difference between the variables in the determinant of career choice among the subjects used. Comparing the mean scores of the influencing factors, parents decision for students career have the highest influence with the mean score of 1.61, followed closely by the parent's income with a mean score of 1.59. Family occupation was next to the parents' income with a mean score of 1.58. Siblings influence on career choice was the next to the family occupation with a mean score of 1.45, parent occupation with a mean score of 1.41 was second to the last of the determinant of career choice of subjects used, while home type (Broken or intact) was the least among the variables that determined the career choice of the subjects. This implies that all these variables contributed or influenced the student's career choice but at a various degree.

7. Discussion

The findings revealed that family background variables have a significant influence on the career choice of secondary school students in Ekiti State Nigeria. This is premised on the fact that the family, irrespective of its type, constitutes the primary social environment of the child. The family dynamic and interaction such as attachment, environment assumed to play a dominant role in the children's career choice. In some cases, children involvement in the family occupation commences early when they notice and have to be involved in such occupation determine the child education and career to choose in a later year. This finding was in line with Khan (2013), who stressed that a child is raised in accordance with values of the family and as he grows he learns, internalizes and concretizes the behaviour patterns to which he is exposed. This may eventually determine the job or career of such an individual. Siblings influence on career choice as revealed in the findings was supported by Madu (2011) and Kniveton (2004) that there is a positive relationship between children's early rearing experiences and their occupational choice since these children spend most of their years at home with their siblings and they naturally regard them as their reference group and significant figures. The few students that were in support if parents' occupation or attached importance to the occupation of their parent may not be unconnected with the predominant rural location subject who has the plan to inherit the occupation or the investment of their parents as a career. This find, however, supports the postulation of Udoh and Sanni (2012) that there is a tendency for families to remain in the same occupation through two to three generations.

8. Conclusion and Recommendation

Generally, it was concluded that family background variables, that is, parents decision, parent occupation, parent income, siblings influence, Home types and family occupations have significant influence on the choice of career among the subject use in study showed that there is tendency for the subject used study glue with their family occupations, while majority of them take to their parent decision on their career choice. Based on the study findings, parent enjoined to always be diligent in doing what they are doing as occupation or career; they should also be good examples to their children. Parents should advice their words accordingly in order to select an appropriate career based on their future ambitions. Counselling unit in the school should put in place a programme that will be of help to these youths in preparing for their future career.

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